

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Deliverable D9.2

Catalogue on environmental and biomonitoring networks Y1

WP9 – T9.2

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¹ PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other program participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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Abstract

This deliverable, called “Catalogue of environmental, food and feed, article and indoor monitoring and human biomonitoring programmes, projects, networks, and other resources” (D9.2), reports on the cross-cutting activities implemented during the first year of PARC for the mapping of environmental monitoring, food and feed monitoring, monitoring of articles and indoor spaces, as well as human biomonitoring (HBM) studies, projects, activities, and networks under Task 9.2 focused on mapping available exposure monitoring capacities. These activities will continue to be carried out for the entire project duration and their outcomes will be updated on the annual bases. In line with the Annual Work Plan, we focused on environmental monitoring and human biomonitoring initiatives in the first year.

To develop an inventory of HBM studies, we took an advantage of the outcomes of HBM4EU and complemented them with a new search within PARC and beyond. As there are overlaps in the inventories developed under HBM4EU (WP7 and WP10/IPCHEM¹) and other projects (e.g. <https://www.birthcohorts.net/>), the main challenge for the development of a comprehensive catalogue has been a precise identification of existing studies. More effort will be needed in Year 2 to cover the whole spectrum of HBM activities and projects.

The first mapping of environmental networks was performed by (i) online survey disseminated through the PARC partners involved in Task 9.2 and the National Hub Contact Points (NHCP) and (ii) manual search on the internet. As a result of these actions, a total of 161 environmental monitoring programmes/projects/datasets were identified and will undergo further scrutiny in Y2.

Keywords

Environmental monitoring; human biomonitoring; metadata; inventory; catalogue; air; water, soil; food and feed; article; indoor; network; questionnaire; scoping review; data platform

¹ IPCHEM is the European Commission’s reference access point for searching, accessing and retrieving chemical occurrence data collected and managed in Europe (<https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>).

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Abbreviations

AWP: Annual Work Plan

BFR: Brominated Flame Retardants

CRA: Chemical Risk Assessment

HBM: Human Biomonitoring

HBM4EU: The European Human Biomonitoring Initiative (GA No 733032)

IPChem: European Commission’s reference access point for searching, accessing and retrieving chemical occurrence data

NHCP: National Hub Contact Points

NTS: Non-Target Screening

OPFR: OrganoPhosphate Flame Retardants

PAH: PolyAromatic Hydrocarbons

PARC: Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

PCB: PolyChlorinated Biphenyl

PFAS: Per- and PolyfluoroAlkylated Substances

POPs: Persistent Organic Pollutants

SC: Stockholm Convention

SOP: Standard Operation Procedure

UNEP: United Nations Environment Programme

WHO: World Health Organisation

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2. Background

The objective of PARC WP9 is to promote **further improvement of existing and development of new infrastructural and human capacities in support of the R&I activities** and integrated risk assessment carried out in PARC (namely WP 4, 5, 6, 8) and beyond. The whole WP was designed with a long-term focus on enhancing the EU experimental capacities, increasing quality, reliability and comparability of newly generated data and mediating an increased access to and effective use of existing resources available within and beyond PARC. These resources include:

- existing environmental (air, water, soil), indoor, article, food and feed monitoring and human biomonitoring programmes and projects, including biobanks and specimen banks storing available samples,
- laboratories offering targeted analyses of priority chemicals and their residues in biotic and abiotic matrices to assess chemical exposures as well as selected markers of biological effects of such exposures, including their SOPs and QA/QC schemes,
- laboratories providing data on high-resolution (non-target) screening (NTS) of biotic and abiotic samples, including their SOPs, data processing pipelines and spectral libraries,
- toxicological laboratories and projects providing systematic hazard data,
- databases storing and providing an access to parameters listed above, including complex information systems,
- data processing, modelling and visualisation tools enhancing use and re/use of existing data.

The goal of Tasks 9.1. and 9.2 is **to perform an inventory of existing resources and develop a comprehensive catalogue increasing their visibility and accessibility to multiple users**. This will require an establishment of synergies with WP3 responsible for communication with the National Hub Contact Points (NHCPs), but also across all PARC research WPs (namely 4, 5, 6, 8) and relevant synergistic projects

(namely EHEN projects). In the close collaboration with WP7 and owners of respective resources, available metadata will be assessed and described whenever possible to increase their findability and accessibility, reliability and effective re-use of existing data.

An important aspect is a sustainability and interoperability of all tools developed under PARC. Therefore, the collaboration will also be established with existing and newly developed research infrastructures (namely ESFRI infrastructures such as EIRENE, BBMRI or ELIXIR) to explore their capacities, existing tools, and options to ensure sustainability of the PARC products (together with WP2).

PARC WP9 will build on the outcomes of the HBM4EU activities, namely on the inventory of laboratory capacities for human biomonitoring in Task 9.1 and the inventory of biomonitoring studies in Task 9.2. However, it needs to go much further and include also all resources needed to assess contamination of environmental matrices, indoor, articles and food and feed, as well as associated hazards and risks. Comprehensive information collected and organized in openly accessible catalogues will serve as a base for analysis of gaps, and definition of strategies for closing these gaps.

These activities will continue to be carried out for the entire duration of the project and their outcomes will be updated on the annual bases. Here we provide an overview of the Year 1 activities and their outcomes.

3. Methodology

This deliverable reports on the outcomes of the cross-cutting activities towards the development of comprehensive catalogues of environmental, indoor, article, and food and feed monitoring, as well as human biomonitoring (HBM) studies, programmes, projects, and networks implemented during the first year of the Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals (PARC) under Task 9.2 focused on “Building exposure monitoring capacities.” The term ‘metadata’ is used throughout the report to describe structured information defining and describing the data collection which is needed to understand, trace and work with the data.

In line with the Year1 (Y1) Annual Working Plan (AWP), Task 9.2 activities focused on three topics: (i) inventory of existing human biomonitoring efforts, (ii) inventory of environmental monitoring efforts and (iii) review of existing software tools suitable for development of comprehensive catalogues.

The inventories of HBM studies and laboratories analysing the priority chemicals in human matrices developed within HB44EU served only as a base for the project activities but have not been organized in searchable catalogues available to wider community of users. This is, however, the ambition of PARC. Therefore, the T9.2 partners carried out a detailed assessment of software tools most suitable for the development of comprehensive catalogues and synergistic projects developing similar catalogues. The outcomes of these surveys were presented and discussed in several T9.2 meetings as well as joint calls with collaborating WPs (WP4, WP7). A final decision will be made at the workshop jointly organised by the WP4, WP7 and WP9 partners at the beginning of Year2 where the outcomes of the T9.2 inventories and the best ways to present them will be discussed.

The inventory of existing HBM studies made use of three HBM4EU outcomes: (i) metadata on HBM studies carried out in HBM4EU available via IPCHEM, (ii) inventory of HBM studies based on the HBM4EU survey, and (iii) HBM monitoring inventory based on the HBM4EU systematic review. These information resources were complemented by a new survey on existing HBM studies distributed to the PARC parties

via Task 4.1 partners, and a preliminary survey of HBM inventories carried out outside the HBM4EU/PARC projects.

Situation is more complicated for environmental, indoor, article, food and feed monitoring efforts which were not in the focus of HBM4EU. They represent a wide range of studies which have not been inventoried yet. Therefore, the AWP1 focused on environmental (air, water, soil) monitoring studies as a priority. Collected data will serve as a pilot for designing the architecture of future catalogues but also the form and scope of future surveys. Remaining matrices will be addressed in following years in a close collaboration with all relevant WPs (4, 7, 8). This applies also for toxicological studies and related data where the scope and parameters of future surveys must be defined in collaboration with WPs 5 and 6. The identification of existing environmental monitoring resources was performed by (i) online survey disseminated through the PARC partners involved in Task 9.2 and the National Hub Contact Points (NHCP) and (ii) web search.

The following chapter describes the outcomes of these pilot inventories but also their limitations and gaps, as well as steps to be taken to obtain more complete and reliable information.

4. Outcomes of Year 1 Activities

4.1. Human Biomonitoring studies

This chapter aims to give an overview of the activities inventorying human biomonitoring efforts carried out in HBM4EU as well as those currently on-going in PARC and other synergistic projects/activities. It also provides recommendations on how to address the identified challenges and which actions are needed to get to a comprehensive catalogue of biomonitoring efforts in Y2.

The main challenge has been a precise identification of existing studies as there were overlaps in the inventories developed under various HBM4EU (WP6, WP7 and WP10/IPCHEM) and PARC (WP4) tasks and other similar efforts.

We have worked with five different sources of information:

1. Metadata on existing HBM studies collected during HBM4EU and made available via IPCHEM;
2. Information on existing HBM studies collected within PARC by Task 4.1 partners;
3. Inventory of HBM studies developed through the HBM4EU survey;
4. Inventory of HBM studies based on the HBM4EU systematic review;
5. Inventories of studies carried out outside the HBM4EU/PARC projects.

As for the outcomes, to date, under the framework of HBM4EU project, 159 studies (existing HBM studies and studies organized within the HBM4EU project) shared metadata with IPCHEM. Another 59 studies that targeted the groups of substances prioritized under the HBM4EU and 117 studies collected through a survey within HBM4EU, were mapped.

The outcomes of these efforts are described below in detail.

4.1.1 Metadata on HBM studies collected during HBM4EU and made available via IPCHEM:

IPCHEM is structured in four modules: Human biomonitoring, Environmental monitoring, Food and Feed monitoring, and Product and indoor air monitoring. To improve the IPCHEM metadata structure, a specific Human biomonitoring metadata template was developed during the HBM4EU project by the WP10 partners in collaboration with the IPCHEM team.

Metadata information was divided into four sections as tabs in the Excel metadata template:

- General information on the data collection including data collection name and description, country covered, language of the data collection, sampling strategy, level of data granularity, starting and ending date of data collection, seasonality, and additional information sources (URLs or DOIs of relevant publications).
- Information on the ethical approval, responsible organisation(s) and contact points, and data access and use conditions.
- Information on the study population including age, sex, weight, height, lifestyle information, etc. (if available).
- Sampling and analytical information for each sample gathered into the data collection and biomarker analysed, such as the types of biological matrices, sampling dates and numbers of collected samples, substance groups analyzed, exposure biomarker names, acronyms and CAS numbers, LODs and LOQs of respective analyses, etc.

Three additional tabs were included to provide:

- terms and definitions in the template,
- code list, e.g. tables with the pre-defined values used to build the drop-down menus,
- list of biomarker list enabling identification of the exposure biomarkers measured.

To date, 159 studies (existing HBM studies and studies organised within the HBM4EU project) shared metadata with IPCHEM and are publicly accessible through IPCHEM (<https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/#discovery>).

4.1.2 Information on HBM studies collected within PARC WP4 by the T4.1 partners:

To develop the General Survey project (P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO) and targeted survey projects under subtask 4.1.1.3, there was a need to get an overview of HBM studies planned in the PARC partner countries. Therefore, a new questionnaire (Excel spreadsheet) was sent to all PARC T4.1 contacts with the request to fill the file with info on their HBM studies.

The specific focus was on:

- i. Studies targeting general population (children, teenagers, adults)
- ii. Targeted studies focused on the following research topics:
 - Pregnant women/prenatal exposure/birth cohorts
 - Exposure through diet in early life: study on breast milk

- Exposure through diet in early life: study on young children: 1-5y
- Study on adults (50-69y): environmental exposures and risk factors for common diseases in the adult population >50y
- Time trends/ policy evaluation
- Hotspot HBM

iii. Other studies not fitting the categories above could also be listed.

The Excel file is available for PARC project partners in the [VITO PARC Sharepoint](#). However, the resulting file should be considered a working document and not a final inventory. The overview of information collected in the survey is provided in table 1.

Table 1 – Information collected in PARC WP4 (T 4.1) survey in order to get an overview of HBM general population studies and targeted studies planned in the PARC partner countries

Info collected	General population studies	Targeted studies	Other
Target group		x	x
EU region		x	x
Country		x	x
Institute		x	x
Sample collection period		x	x
Short study description - (<i>open text</i>)		x	x
Expected total sample size of the study- (<i>open text</i>)		x	/
Matrices planned to be collected (urine, blood, breast milk, other) - (<i>column of matrices to be marked with "X"</i>)		x	/

Comment - <i>(open text)</i>		x	x
<p>Substances - <i>(column of substances planned for analysis to be marked with "X")</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Mercury ● Toxic metals and metalloids (e.g.: Al, Co, Mn, Cd, Pb, Cu, Zn, Ni, Cr, W, natural U, Bi, Be, Mn, Ni, As, Li, V, Sb) ● Metals in batteries: Co, Ni, Li, nanoforms of Co and Ni ● Acrylamide ● Per- and Polyfluoroalkylated substances (PFAS) ● Brominated flame retardants (BFR, including novel BFR such as TBBPA, DBDPE, decabromo-diphenyl ethane, CAS: 84852-53-9, EC: 284-366-9), Organophosphate flame retardants (OPFR, including TDCPP) ● Biocides with a focus on glyphosate, Pyrethroids, Carbamates, Dithiocarbamates, Organophosphates ● Fungicides including SDHI fungicides (boscalid, bixafen, fluxapyroxad), Azoles (imazalil, ipconazole, metconazole, penconazole, prochloraz, tebuconazole, tetraconazole), Dithiocarbamates, famoxadone and dimoxystrobin; Isothiazolinones (CIT/MIT, BIT), Triazole derivative metabolites (TDM) ● Phthalates and substitutes, FCM phthalate substitutes, DEHTP (Bis(2-ethylhexyl) terephthalate) CAS 6422-86-2 ● Persistent Organic Pollutants of Increasing Concern such as Dechloranes, Chlorinated paraffins and Chloronaphtalenes, Dioxins and PCBs ● UV filters (Salicylates, Cinnamates and Benzophenones). ● Mixtures (including contaminants, e.g., Mycotoxins and plant contaminants, and air pollutants with EDC properties) ● PAHs ● Bisphenols and metabolites (BADGE/DGEBA, Bisphenol-A-diglycidylether / Diglycidylether of Bisphenol A, CAS Number: 1675- 		x	x

<p>54-3 EC Number: 216-823-5 and Tetrabromo-bisphenol A (TBBPA); 3-1 Tetrabromobisphenol A)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Emerging substances, unknowns, non-targeted screening ● Substances with potential to bioaccumulate in air-breathing organisms ● Nanomaterials, nano plastics, nano titanium dioxide ● Mycotoxins, in particular Ochratoxin A (CAS 303-47-9). Emerging and endocrine active mycotoxins. ● Endocrine disruptors ● Styrene ● MOAH Mineral oil aromatic hydrocarbons ● Synthetic fragrances (OTNE-Tetramethyl acetyloctahydronaphthalene, Galaxolide, Lysmeral/Lilial CAS 80-54-6, Polycyclic musks, Lyrall CAS 31906-04-4, Hydroxycitronellal ● Industrial solvents (e.g., BTEX metabolites, dry cleaning solvents, paint solvents) ● Medical substances: occupational ● Aluminum and manganese: occupational ● Pyrazole 			
Point(s) of contact - <i>(open text)</i>		x	x
specific focus/interest - <i>(open text)</i>	x	x	x
Implementation level (regional/national)	x		
Includes male and female subjects. (Yes/no)	x		
<p>Expected age coverage:</p> <p>Children: 6-11</p> <p>Teenagers: 12-19</p> <p>Adults: open text</p>	x		

Interest in add-on topics: (column with topic of interest to be marked with "X")	x	x	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • early effect biomarkers • novel analytical techniques (NTS, suspect screening) • connecting HBM to environmental monitoring data (indoor air/dust), soil, emission, etc. • novel sampling techniques (micro-sampling, non-invasive sampling, self-sampling) • oversampling of environmental hotspot area 			
Time points available (asked for time trend topic only) - <i>(open text)</i>		x	
hotspot/ contamination origin (asked for hotspot study only) - <i>(open text)</i>		x	
Proposed geographical area (asked for hotspot study only) - <i>(open text)</i>		x	

To date, information on 184 studies was collected in this survey. They include:

- General population: 62 studies (20 on children, 18 on teenagers and 24 on adults).
- Targeted studies: 85 studies
 - 18 studies on pregnant women/prenatal exposure/birth cohorts
 - 7 studies on exposure through diet in early life (study on breast milk)
 - 11 studies on exposure through diet in early life: study on young children: 1-5y
 - 19 studies on adults (40-69y): environmental exposures and risk factors for common diseases in the adult population >39y
 - 12 studies on time trends/ policy evaluation
 - 18 studies on hotspot HBM - connected with ambient monitoring (water, soil, air,..).
- Other: 37 studies.

4.1.3 Inventory of HBM studies identified through the HBM4EU survey

An online questionnaire (later transformed into an HBM web platform) was also developed earlier within Task 7.1 of the HBM4EU project to compile a list of concluded, ongoing or planned studies (including

available biobank samples) within the consortium targeting the groups of substances prioritized in the project. The questionnaire was divided into nine domains, each of them consisting of multiple parameters (263 parameters in total) (Table 2).

Table 2 – Structure of the online questionnaire under HBM4EU

Domain	Info collected	Number of indicators
General information	Overall information on the study, namely name and acronym, principal investigator, responsible institution, contacts, type of study, implementation level, country and language of data collection, beginning and ending date, budget and funding institutions, and ethical approval	25
Target population and method of selection of participants	Information on study design, study setting, target groups (age and sample size), inclusion and exclusion criteria, control group, sampling, recruitment and consent procedures	63
Fieldwork	Information on period of data collection, questionnaire used, groups of substances under study, collected indicators	36
Other data	Information on collected indicators	76
Quality control procedures	Information on preanalytical quality assurance/quality control, internal quality control procedures, standard operating procedures, accreditation of the laboratory and other certifications	10
Data protection, availability, and conditions of access and use	Information on data storage and access	16
Communication	Information on the dissemination of the study to the public authorities, to the study participants, to the health institutions, to the scientific community and to the general public	19
Obstacles, shortcomings and difficulties	Information on constraints and difficulties in general and related to participants' recruitment and data collection	17
Additional information	Other relevant information not covered in the other dimensions	1

After the initial launch of the questionnaire in 2017, and the further updates in 2018 and 2022, a total of 117 studies were collected.

4.1.4 Inventory of HBM studies identified through the systematic review performed during HBM4EU

A systematic review (not yet published) was undertaken within HBM4EU WP6 (T6.2) to identify HBM studies in Europe (from 2015 on) and their primary funding sources in order to characterize the current research and funding gaps, both in terms of geographical coverage as well as chemical substances studied. The search only targeted the groups of substances prioritised under the HBM4EU initiative.

The collected information included bibliometric data of the identified papers of each study, name and acronym of the study, country where the study was conducted, level of implementation, sample size and target population, chemical substances analysed, and funding information.

A total of 59 studies were included.

4.1.5 Inventories performed outside HBM4EU/PARC

The inventory of birth cohorts has been developed and continuously updated with support of multiple EU projects (Lifepath, HELIX, ATHLETE, EXPANSE etc.). A searchable database can be found at <https://www.birthcohorts.net/>. All cohorts included in this inventory were recruited before or during the pregnancy, or – at the latest - at birth. They have at least 300 mother-child pairs and at least one year of the follow-up. Key information collected include a study design, number of participants, available biological samples and data (e.g. on socioeconomic conditions, nutrition and lifestyle, exposures, health outcomes, and contact persons). There are also other inventories outside HBM4EU/PARC, such as <https://www.maelstrom-research.org/page/catalogue>.

Information on the biomonitoring studies were also organized, for example, within the Stockholm Convention on Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs) which is a globally binding agreement focusing on the protection of health and the environment from the negative impact of listed manmade chemicals. In the mid-1980s and early 1990s, the World Health Organization (WHO) coordinated two exposure studies on concentrations of polychlorinated biphenyls (PCB), polychlorinated dibenzo-*p*-dioxins (PCDD), and polychlorinated dibenzofurans (PCDF) in human milk. After adopting the SC in 2001, WHO and the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) agreed to collaborate in joint studies starting in 2004. Between 2000 and 2019, WHO and UNEP jointly implemented additional five global studies on concentrations of POPs in human milk with the participation of 82 countries (50 of them participating in more than one study). The seven rounds of WHO/UNEP human milk exposure studies are the largest global survey on human tissues with a harmonized protocol spanning over the longest time period and carried out in a uniform format. The data are publicly available in the Data Warehouse of the SC Global Monitoring Plan (GMP DWH)

4.2 Environmental monitoring studies

The existing environmental monitoring programmes, projects, network and studies were identified by (i) the online survey disseminated through the PARC partners involved in Task 9.2 and the National Hub Contact Points (NHCP) and (ii) the web search.

This chapter describes the results of the pilot data collection, reliability and limitations of the chosen methods. It also outlines necessary future steps to obtain relevant, complete, and reliable information.

4.2.1 Information on environmental studies collected within the PARC WP4 by the T4.2 partners in the online survey

A survey organized as a self-administered online questionnaire was used to obtain information on the European national and regional monitoring studies. The questionnaire was distributed through the PARC's National Hub Contact Points (NHCP), partners involved in task 9.2 and other relevant partners.

The questionnaire contained 27 questions most of which (21 questions) could be answered using a free text. Only three questions seeking the respondent's identification were mandatory as they were relevant to all subjects. All the others were optional, as not all the questions were relevant to all subjects.

The questions asked in the survey were structured into six groups:

1. Contact of the respondent
2. Monitoring effort – identification of the monitoring programme and available information sources
3. Sampling design – temporal and spatial description
4. Data handling– identification of data repositories
5. Laboratories – identification of the laboratories where the samples were analyzed
6. Compounds and matrices – list of substances measured in target matrices

Overview of monitoring networks (projects/studies)

Table 3 contains an overview of the monitoring efforts/data sets that were identified in the survey.

Table 3 – Results of the on-line survey

Full name of the monitoring programme/project/network/study	Website address	Country	Matrix
Ambient air quality monitoring networks in Wallonia	https://www.wallonair.be/en	BE	outdoor air
Barcelona Life Study Cohort	https://projectebisc.org/en/home/	ES	Water
Caracterizacion de Contaminacion Antropogénica, Utilidad Como Marcadores	www.risama.es	ES	Multiple
Environment and health in children day care centres		PT	
European Monitoring Evaluation Programmme (EMEP-VAG-CAMP)	https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/calidad-y-evaluacion-ambiental/temas/atmosfera-y-calidad-del-aire/	ES	outdoor air
EXPO – the national exposure database Norway	https://stami.no/vare-tjenester/expo/	NO	
Geochemical Atlas of Europe	http://weppi.gtk.fi/publ/foregsatlas/disclaimer.php		
Geriatric study in Portugal on health effects of air quality in elderly care centres	geria.webnode.page	PT	Air
Global Mercury Observation System	https://www.gmos.eu/		Multiple
Groundwater quality monitoring network		CZ	Water

Healthy Aging in Industrial Region (project)	https://www.iem.cas.cz/vyzkum/oddele ni/oddeleni-geneticke-toxikologie-a-epigenetiky/ ; https://www.4haie.cz/en/haie-2/	CZ	food and feed
HELIX/ATHLETE H2020 EU projects - Advancing Tools for Human Early Lifecourse Exposome Research and Translation	https://athleteproject.eu/about/	NO, ES, GB, FR, LT, GR	outdoor air, water
How indoor air quality can affect child allergies and asthma		PT	Indoor
Impact of transplacental exposure to tobacco smoke in the DNA of newborn. Genetic and epigenetic effects	neogeneprojecto.wixsite.com/neogene?lang=en	PT	indoor dust
Infancia y Medio Ambiente (INMA project: Environment and Childhood Project)		ES	food and feed, water
LCMA-UPC Volatile Organic Compounds Monitoring Network	https://lcma.upc.edu/ca	ES	
Monitoring of water and food		SK	
Multiple projects focused on circular economy with monitoring activities in Flanders	www.OVAM.be	BE	waste
Multiple national and international projects.	https://www.graq.isep.ipp.pt/	PT	soil, water
National Health Monitoring program - Indoor exposure		LU	indoor dust
National monitoring network on air quality	www.shmu.sk	SK	outdoor air
National monitoring plans for EU	multiple	FI	food and feed
National Water Monitoring Network	http://nmwn.ypeka.gr	GR	Water
Navarre Air Quality Surveillance Network	https://www.navarra.es/es/calidaddelaire	ES	outdoor air
NORMAN network - Network of reference laboratories, research centres and related organisations for monitoring of emerging environmental substances	https://www.norman-network.net/	international	Freshwater, marine, biota, air, soil, sediment, indoor environment, microplastics
Official Governmental Monitoring & Control Program of the Republic of Cyprus	https://www.moh.gov.cy/moh/sgl/sgl.nsf/index_en/index_en?OpenDocument	CY	indoor air, water, soil, sediment, food and feed, material articles
Outdoor air pollution	https://qualar.apambiente.pt/	PT	
PARC		pan-European	Air, water, soil, food and feed, indoor, articles
Pesticide Surveillance and Control Network in the Atmosphere of the Valencian Region (Spain)		ES	
RBD (River Basin Districts - Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica y el Reto Demográfico MITERD) / CSIC (Centro Superior de Investigaciones Científicas) Monitoring programs from Water Frame Directive / Watch List surveillance program	https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/agua/temas/estado-y-calidad-de-las-aguas/	ES	Water
Red de biomonitorización de metales pesados y HAP de La Rioja (Heavy Metals and PAH Biomonitoring Network of La Rioja (Spain))	https://www.larioja.org/medio-ambiente/es/calidad-aire-cambio-climatico/calidad-aire/red-biomonitorizacion-metales-pesados-rioja	ES	material articles
Red de Contaminación Atmosférica Ceuta	https://www.ceutaica.es/	ES	outdoor air

Redes de Observacion Ambiental de Galicia (Aire, Agua Natudes)	https://www.meteogalicia.gal/web/inicio.action	ES	air, water
Réseau wallon de contrôle de la qualité des sédiments des cours d'eau navigable	www.issep.be	BE	Sediment
Réseau wallon de contrôle de la qualité des sédiments des cours d'eau non navigable	www.issep.be	BE	Sediment
Réseau wallon de contrôle des biotes	www.issep.be	BE	Biota
Réseau wallon de contrôle des eaux de surface / souterraine ...	www.issep.be	BE	
Réseau wallon de contrôle des eaux de surface	www.issep.be	BE	Water
Réseau wallon de contrôle des eaux des lacs	www.issep.be	BE	Water
Réseau wallon de contrôle des eaux industrielles	www.issep.be	BE	Water
Réseau wallon de contrôle des eaux souterraines	www.issep.be	BE	Water
Rhone Sediment Observatory (Observatoire des Sédiments du Rhône)	http://www.graie.org/osr/	FR	Sediment
SCIRI: Sistema de Intercambio Rápido de Información	https://www.aesan.gob.es/AECOSAN/web/seguridad_alimentaria/seccion/alertas_alimentarias.htm	ES	Food
Sistema de vigilancia, predicción e información de la calidad del aire del Ayuntamiento de Madrid	https://airedemadrid.madrid.es/portal/site/calidadaire	ES	outdoor air
Solid matrices monitoring network	www.chmi.cz	CZ	sediment, water
Special purpose monitoring network - for monitoring groundwater pollution		SK	Water
State Health Supervision, Official inspection of food	https://www.vzbb.sk/index.php	SK	Water, food and feed
State network for continuous air quality monitoring	http://iszz.azo.hr/iskzl/index.html , https://meteo.hr/index_en.php	HR	outdoor air
Tackling hazardous substances pollution in the Danube River Basin by Measuring, Modelling-based Management and Capacity building (project)	https://www.interreg-danube.eu/approved-projects/danube-hazard-m3c	RO, BG, HU, AU	Water
Water Framework Directive Network; Nitrate Directive Network (for surface water and groundwater)	https://eau.gouvernement.lu/fr.html	LU	Water
Water quality and safety	https://www.insa.min-saude.pt/	PT	Water

It can be seen that we received a mix of information on on-going monitoring efforts and responsible institutions (often the long-term monitoring activities are carried out by the relevant institution in support of the national or European legislation and do not even have a fixed title), websites summarizing multiple efforts, short-term national and international projects as well as collaborative networks. More work will be required in the following years to sort out primary monitoring programmes, monitoring campaigns carried out in support of various population studies, various international projects and integrative databases. In some cases, the same data could have been presented by several institutions, and the ownership of data must be also clarified.

Analysis of survey results

55 subjects filled the questionnaire. A ratio between proper and missing answers can be seen in following tables (a difference between the total number of answers (55) and a sum of useful and missing answers are the answers that were not relevant for a subject).

a. Contact to the respondent

The first three questions helped identifying the respondent so that missing or incomplete information can be filled in later, if necessary. The respondent provided his/her name, e-mail, and the name of the institution on behalf of which (s)he is completing the questionnaire. Filling these fields was mandatory and data were available for all 55 respondents.

b. Monitoring network – identification of the monitoring programme/network and sources of available information

There were some uncertainties in identification of the monitoring programmes: (i) some of them are only registered under the institution and do not have a specific name or acronym, (ii) some were reported in languages other than English, (iii) data from national programmes are often reported as parts of specific networks, therefore the ownership of data (responsible institution) and proper contacts are not always clear, (iv) there is a chance that same data can be reported by multiple institutions. (v) web page information is not always clear/complete. An overview of responses is in table 4.

Table 4 – An overview of responses identifying the monitoring programmes and related data sets.

	number of responses	number of NA
Full name of the monitoring network (project/study)	55	0
Acronym for the monitoring network (project/study)	38	15
Data source	46	9
Data owner – institution	44	11
Point of contact – email	42	13
Website address	38	17

Note: NA, Not Available

c. Description of the sampling design (temporal and spatial coverage)

About 50% of the reported monitoring programmes were established more than a decade ago, and 60% are on-going. Some 90% of responses report on the national or regional (e.g. a region within one country) monitoring programmes. Numbers of sites in reported programmes are highly variable, and some programmes do not use GIS coordinates to identify their sites.

Table 5 - Questionnaire's responses on sampling designs

	number of responses	number of NA
Start of monitoring (year)	39	14
End of monitoring (year/ongoing)	43	12

Geographical scale	50	5
Countries (2 letters ISO code) https://countrycode.org/	33	22
Number of sampling sites	40	11
Site coordinates	45	10

Note: NA, Not Available

d. Data repositories

Only about 50% of the data owners responded inquiries on their data repositories, contact points and web links were rarely provided. Some 25% reported on-line availability of their data and only about a half of them provided also a download link.

Table 6: Questionnaire's responses on data repositories

	number of responses	number of NA
Full name of the database	28	25
Acronym for the database	16	39
Online link	13	42
Data download link	6	48
Data accessibility (i.e., public access online/private access/on demand)	27	28
Format data export (i.e., Excel/ csv/ xml/ pdf)	25	29
Database contact point	20	35
Type of data	36	19

Note: NA, Not available

e. Supporting laboratories

The survey identified 41 laboratories analysing samples from reposted studies. These laboratories are located in 18 European countries.

f. Collected matrices and target compounds

Information on collected matrices and target substances was reported from 35 monitoring networks. Table 7 summarizes target matrices and table 7 groups of analysed substances. Air and water are the most commonly monitored matrices and PAHs and PFAS the most commonly analyzed substances.

Table 7 – Matrices collected in reported environmental monitoring programmes

water	21
outdoor air	9
food and feed	5
sediment	4
material (articles)	3
indoor dust	2
soil	2
indoor air	1
NA	3

Table 8 – Substance groups analyzed in reported environmental monitoring programmes

PAHs	27
PFAS	19
Pharmaceuticals	12
PCBs	12
Dioxin-like PCBs	12
Bisphenols	10
PBDEs	9
HCBD – hexachlorobutadiene	7
PCDDs/Fs	6
Paraffins	6
Phthalates	5
Sweeteners	3
OPFRs	2
Microcystins	2
Pesticides – organochlorine	1
Pesticides – currently used	1
Pesticides – pyrethroids	1
Pesticides – drines	1
Pesticides – other	1

Conclusions

This pilot survey provided preliminary data important for our discussions on the architecture of the future PARC Data Hub bringing together relevant information on availability of data for chemical risk assessment as well as designing/optimizing processes for developing and updating such information portal. The first step is the development of a metadata database with a simple structure that is user-friendly to allow for editing data from multiple users but sufficiently robust to host a variety of data from reported programmes. This will serve as a source for a future interactive data hub.

4.2.2 Scoping review

To identify existing environmental monitoring programmes, projects and networks and related metadata available online, a scoping review was carried out on the internet.

We collected data on:

- name of the monitoring effort,
- target matrices,
- web link to available metadata (and data if available),
- responsible institution (data owner).

Several complementary strategies were applied for metadata collection: (i) searching for the existing environmental databases such as EBAS (<https://ebas.nilu.no/>), IPCHEM (Information Platform for Chemical Monitoring, <https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>), GMP (Global Monitoring Plan, <https://pops-gmp.org/>), GENASIS (<https://www.genasis.cz/index-en.php>), (ii) harvesting information from the websites of large institutions (e.g., WHO or EEA) and finally, (iii) a systematic internet search using a combination of keywords (i.e. environmental monitoring, air, water, sediment, soil, biota, pollution, contaminant, and European).

Table 3 shows the results of the scoping review, again in the alphabetical order of the names of monitoring efforts. As in the previous case, it was not always possible to identify the name of the monitoring programme as some of them were listed under the responsible institutions or the supporting project (marked with an asterisk).

Table 9 – Results of the scoping review

Monitoring programme/project/network/study	Website address	Country	Matrix
Acid Waters Monitoring Network (previously Upland Waters)	https://uk-air.defra.gov.uk/networks/network-info?view=uw	UK	water
Aerosols, Clouds, and Trace gases Research InfraStructure (ACTRIS)	https://ebas-data.nilu.no/	international	outdoor Air
Air Quality*	https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/	international	outdoor Air
Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme (AMAP)	https://ebas-data.nilu.no/	international	outdoor Air
Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme (AMAP)	https://www.ices.dk/data/assessment-tools/Pages/amap-ahat.aspx https://www.amap.no/ahat	international	biota
Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme (AMAP)	https://litterandmicroplastics.amap.no/	international	litter/microplastics
Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme (AMAP) Project Portal and AMAP Thematic Data Centres *	http://projects.amap.no/directory/amap/ https://www.amap.no/about/data-compilation	international	multiple

Automatic Hydrocarbon Network	https://uk-air.defra.gov.uk/networks/network-info?view=hc	UK	outdoor Air
Automatic London Network	https://uk-air.defra.gov.uk/networks/network-info?view=aln	UK	outdoor Air
Automatic Urban and Rural Network (AURN)	https://uk-air.defra.gov.uk/networks/network-info?view=aurn	UK	outdoor Air
Baltic hazardous and agricultural releases reduction (Balthazar)*	https://helcom.fi/helcom-at-work/projects/balthazar/	international	water
Basal Soil Monitoring (ÚKZÚZ)	https://eagri.cz/public/web/file/520923/Publikace_25_let_Monitoring_Zemedelskych_pud_1992_2013.pdf	CZ	soil
Regional monitoring - Beroun area *	https://data.genasis.cz/#	CZ	outdoor air, sediment, soil, water
BIOSoil*	https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/	international	soil
Catalan Water Agency monitoring program*	https://aca.gencat.cat/ca/laigua/seguiment-i-control/xarxes-de-control/	ES	water
Compendium of botanicals*	https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/data-report/compendium-botanicals	international	food and feed
Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche - Water Research Institute (CNR-IRSA)*	https://www.cnr.it/en/institute/069/water-research-institute-irsa	IT	water
Convention on the Protection of the Rhine (ICPR)*	https://www.iksr.org/de/	GE	water
Coordinated Environmental Monitoring Programme (CEMP)*	https://odims.ospar.org/en/	international	water
Czech Hydrometeorological Institute (CHMI)*	https://www.chmi.cz/?tab=2	CZ	outdoor Air
EFSA - Chemical monitoring data*	https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/resources/data-collection-chemicals	international	food and feed
EFSA Comprehensive European Food Consumption Database*	https://data.europa.eu/data/datasets/the-efsa-comprehensive-european-food-consumption-database?locale=en	international	food and feed
EFSA CONTAMINANTS*	https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/	international	food and feed
EFSA MCPD*	https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/	international	food and feed
EFSA MOPER*	https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/	international	food and feed
EFSA MYCOTOXINS*	https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/	international	food and feed
EFSA PAS*	https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/	international	food and feed
EFSA VMPR*	https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/	international	food and feed
Emergent pollutants in environmental components (EMERTOX)*	https://data.genasis.cz/#	CZ	outdoor air, sediment, water
EMODNETCHEM*	https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/	international	biota, water
EMPODAT (NORMAN)*	https://www.normandata.eu/nds/empodat/	international	indoor air, outdoor air, biota soil, water
Environmental Monitoring in the Black Sea – phase I (EMBLAS)	https://emblasproject.org/	international	water
Environmental Monitoring in the Black Sea – phase II (EMBLAS)	https://emblasproject.org/	international	water
Environmental Specimen Bank*	https://umweltprobenbank.de/en/documents	GE	multiple
Estonian Environmental Research Center*	https://klab.ee/teenused/keskkonnauuringud/	EE	multiple
EU Pesticides Database*	https://food.ec.europa.eu/plants/pesticides/eu-pesticides-database_en	international	food and feed
Europe Air PUF*	https://data.pops-gmp.org	international	outdoor air

European Environment Information and Observation Network (EIONET) - datasets*	http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/datasets.jsp	international	multiple
European Indoor Air Monitoring and Exposure Assessment Project*	https://data.jrc.ec.europa.eu/collection/airmex	international	indoor air, outdoor air
European Monitoring and Evaluation Programme	https://ebas-data.nilu.no/	international	outdoor air
FATE*	https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/	international	water
Global Atmosphere Passive Sampling (GAPS)	https://data.pops-gmp.org	international	outdoor air
Global Atmosphere Watch (GAW)	https://ebas-data.nilu.no/	international	outdoor air
Global Environment Facility – Air	https://data.pops-gmp.org	international	outdoor air
Green data for health – catalogue*	https://gd4h.ecologie.gouv.fr/en/catalogue	FR	multiple
Heavy Metals Network	https://uk-air.defra.gov.uk/networks/network-info?view=metals	UK	outdoor air
Helsinki Commission	https://ebas-data.nilu.no/	international	outdoor air
Helsinki Commission (HELCOM; Baltic Marine Environment Protection Commission)	https://indicators.helcom.fi/	international	biota, sediment, litter/microplastics
IDRIP*	https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/	international	water
Implementation of MSFD (Marine Strategy Framework Directive)*	https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/marine-and-coastal-environment/implementation-marine-strategy-framework-directive_en	international	water
International Elbe Monitoring Programme	https://www.ikse-mkol.org/en/themen/gewaesserguete/international-es-messnetz-und-internationales-messprogramm	international	water
IPCHEM (Information Platform for Chemical Monitoring)	https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/	international	multiple
ISPRAPESTICIDES*	https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/	international	water
ISPRAPESTICIDESAGGREGATED*	https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/	international	water
JERICO-S3 TRANSNATIONAL ACCESS (TA)*	https://www.jerico-ri.eu/ta/	international	water
South Moravian Region	https://data.genasis.cz/#	CZ	outdoor air
Joint Danube Survey	https://www.icpdr.org/main/activities-projects/joint-danube-survey http://www.danubesurvey.org/jds4/	international	water
Kosetice observatory	https://data.genasis.cz/#	CZ	outdoor air, deposition, plants, sediment, soil, water
Liberec region*	https://data.genasis.cz/#	CZ	outdoor air, plants, soil
Locally-managed automatic monitoring	https://uk-air.defra.gov.uk/networks/network-info?view=nondefraaqmon	UK	outdoor air
LUCAS	https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/	international	soil
Mediterranean Action Plan (MAP)*	https://www.unep.org/unepmap/	international	water
Mokra regional monitoring	https://data.genasis.cz/#	CZ	soil
MonAirNet*	https://data.genasis.cz/#	international	outdoor air, deposition, plants
AQUA-MONET	https://data.genasis.cz/#	international	water
MONET – CEEC	https://data.genasis.cz/#	international	outdoor air, soil

MONET – CZ	https://data.genasis.cz/#	international	outdoor air, soil
MONET – EU	https://data.genasis.cz/#	international	outdoor air
Monitoring Network in the Alpine Region for persistent and other organic pollutants*	https://data.pops-gmp.org	international	outdoor air
Monitoring of Persistent Pollutants in the Alps	https://data.pops-gmp.org	international	outdoor air
Monitoring of the ecological quality of rivers, transitional and coastal waters according to WFD 2000/60/EE*	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32018D0229&from=EN	international	water
NAIADES*	naiades.eaufrance.fr	FR	biota, soil, water, sediment
National Air Pollution Monitoring Network	https://www.bafu.admin.ch/bafu/en/home/topics/air/state/data/national-air-pollution-monitoring-network--nabel-.html	CH	outdoor air
National Groundwater Monitoring	https://www.bafu.admin.ch/bafu/en/home/topics/water/info-specialists/state-of-waterbodies/state-of-groundwater/naqua-national-groundwater-monitoring.html	CH	water
National River Monitoring and Survey Programme (NADUF)	https://www.bafu.admin.ch/bafu/en/home/topics/water/state/water--monitoring-networks/national-surface-water-quality-monitoring-programme--nawa-/national-river-monitoring-and-survey-programme--naduf-.html	CH	water
National Surface Water Quality Monitoring Programme (NAWA)	https://www.bafu.admin.ch/bafu/en/home/topics/water/state/water--monitoring-networks/national-surface-water-quality-monitoring-programme--nawa-.html	CH	water
Non-Automatic Hydrocarbon Network	https://uk-air.defra.gov.uk/networks/network-info?view=nahc	UK	outdoor air
NORMAN Database System*	https://www.normandata.eu/nds/	international	multiple
OFFICAIR*	https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/	international	indoor air, outdoor air
OpenFoodTox*	https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/data-report/chemical-hazards-database-openfoodtox	international	food
Particle Numbers and Concentrations Network	https://uk-air.defra.gov.uk/networks/network-info?view=particle	UK	outdoor air
PHARMSUBA*	https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/	international	indoor air, soil, water, sediment
Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAH)	https://uk-air.defra.gov.uk/networks/network-info?view=pah	UK	outdoor air
POP-Dioxin database*	https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/	international	outdoor air, biota, soil, water
POPs monitoring in CZ (ÚKZÚZ)	https://data.genasis.cz/#	international	plants, sediment, soil
River Basin Management Plans*	https://www.gov.uk/guidance/river-basin-management-plans-updated-2022#strategic-environmental-assessment	UK	water
Scottish Environment Protection Agency*	https://www.sepa.org.uk/environment/environmental-data/	UK	outdoor air, water
SINPHONIE*	https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/	international	indoor air, outdoor air
Spolana*	https://data.genasis.cz/#	CZ	outdoor air, soil, water

The European air quality database (AIRBASE)*	https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/#showmetadata/AIRBASE	international	outdoor air
The International Commission for the Protection of Lake Geneva (CIPEL)	https://www.cipel.org/en/suivi-scientifique/campagnes-suivi/	international	water
The International Commission on the Protection of the Oder against Pollution (ICPO)*	http://www.mkoo.pl/index.php?mid=1&lang=EN	international	water
The Swedish Monitoring Programme*	https://www.naturvardsverket.se/en/international/environmental-monitoring/environmental-monitoring-program-areas/	SE	outdoor air
Toxic Organic Micro Pollutants (TOMPs) Networks	https://uk-air.defra.gov.uk/networks/network-info?view=tomps	UK	outdoor air
TROLL/ Trollhaugen – Air Monitoring in Antarctica	https://www.nilu.com/facility/nilus-observatories-and-monitoring-stations/trollhaugen-observatory/	international	outdoor air
UK Eutrophying & Acidifying Network (UKEAP)	https://uk-air.defra.gov.uk/networks/network-info?view=ukeap	UK	outdoor air
UK Marine Strategy*	https://consult.defra.gov.uk/marine/updated-uk-marine-strategy-part-two-marine-monitor/supporting_documents/marinestrategyparttwoconsultationdocument.pdf	UK	water
UK Urban NO2 Network	https://uk-air.defra.gov.uk/networks/network-info?view=UUNN	UK	outdoor air
UK-Norway Transect	https://www.nilu.com/publication/29324/	UK	outdoor air
UNEP – Water*	https://data.pops-gmp.org	international	water
UNEP/WHO - Human milk	https://data.pops-gmp.org	international	human milk
Veterinary Substances DataBase (VSBD)*	https://sitem.herts.ac.uk/aeru/vsdb/index.htm	UK	food and feed
Water framework directive (WFD)*	https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/	international	biota, water
Water Information System for Europe (WISE)*	https://water.europa.eu/	international	water
WATERBASETCM*	https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/	international	biota, water
WATERQUALITY*	https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/	international	biota, water, sediment
WATCHLIST*	https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/	international	water
Zlin region*	https://data.genasis.cz/#	CZ	outdoor air, sediment, soil, water

The search results can be clustered into the following groups:

1. Monitoring programmes and networks (e.g., EMEP, AMAP, MONET – the monitoring programmes are often carried out at the national levels and coordinated internationally at the level of the network)
2. Institutions in charge of regulatory monitoring (e.g., Czech Hydrometeorological Institute, Estonian Environmental Research Center)
3. Databases hosting and presenting data of (often multiple) monitoring programmes (e.g., EBAS, IPCHEM or NORMAN Database System)
4. Short-term collaborative projects (MONAIRNET)
5. Projects pulling together data from multiple monitoring networks (e.g. European Environment Information and Observation Network (EIONET) - datasets, Green data for health - catalogue).

Metadata found in dedicated web pages of longitudinal programmes and networks, as well as dedicated database systems are usually sufficiently robust while remaining resources rarely enable retrieving sufficient metadata.

Conclusions

The internet search is an important step in development of a comprehensive inventory of available monitoring data, however, there are several challenges: (i) search parameters need further refinements, (ii) significant overlaps with other surveys (such as a PARC survey) must be expected and duplicities removed, (iii) a quality of metadata available for various monitoring programmes/networks vary significantly, (iv) more information should be harvested directly from the programmes/networks but it is a time-consuming process (and relevant contacts are not always findable), (v) short-term collaborative projects produce a large volume of useful data but are most difficult to find/describe.

5. Report on technical solutions for building catalogues of environmental/HBM programmes, supporting laboratories, and related data sources

There is a general requirement to make all data generated in PARC FAIR. This includes also structured and curated results and outcomes of multiple surveys conducted in several PARC WPs.

To support these efforts, a PARC Chemical Risk Assessment (CRA) Data Hub is being developed in WP7 to provide internal and external users with an access to

- chemical risk assessment-relevant resources (metadata on monitoring and biomonitoring programmes, laboratory capacities, databases, data processing workflows, models etc.),
- data storage capacities,
- data management and FAIRification tools

PARC CRA Data Hub will provide a hosting platform for data from multiple surveys and an interactive dashboard capable of presenting interlinked information from such surveys.

- Following inventory types will be given a priority in early iterations: environmental monitoring and biomonitoring programmes (including population cohorts with an HBM element),
- Databases and repositories
- Models and data processing pipelines

5.1 Inventories and catalogues

CRA Data Hub will host the results of conducted inventories and surveys with a goal of

- storing information in a structured and well-documented format,

- providing an access point and a storage capacity for the survey results,
- interlinking information from various surveys (on (bio)monitoring efforts, protocols, labs, standard operation procedures and QA/QC schemes), repositories, models, etc.),
- mapping to semantic terms (controlled vocabularies, ontologies) in compliance with PARC Data Policy and FAIR data implementation decisions,
- APIs for interoperability – SPARQL, REST, etc.

Such interlinks will help future users to implement complex studies (e.g. to find the programmes providing samples, laboratories with relevant expertise and sufficient capacity, databases hosting relevant data, etc.). They will also enable advanced search queries.

5.2 Interactive dashboards and search for inventories

CRA Data Hub will provide a set of interactive dashboards with search and filtering functionalities on top of the single database of inventories (see Figure 2).

Full-text search

- Title
- Description
- Annotation

Parametric search (additional filtering criteria)

- General attributes
 - A chemical substance / group of substances
 - Country
 - Time range
 - Material/matrix
 - CRA Domain
- Domain-specific attributes
 - Labs
 - Accreditation
 - QA-QC procedures
 - Monitoring networks
 - Type of monitoring

Results are organized into facets according to the type of record providing both

- Specific information, and
- Interlinks with other survey entities

Figure 1 – Possible illustrative layout of the PARC data hub and survey dashboard

5.3 Basic insights on content

Further iterations of PARC CRA Data Hub will focus on gathering basic content statistics of tracked entities so we can describe how many samples/records are available (see Figure 2 as an example). This approach is especially relevant for monitoring networks or databases.

Figure 2 – A screenshot from the existing GENESIS portal (www.genesis.cz), the module “Data availability – Parameters on site in time”

6. Conclusions and next steps

Numerous challenges were identified in the pilot phase of the inventory development that need to be addressed before drafting the architecture of the inventory part of the PARC Data Hub:

- Heterogeneity of metadata structures used in existing data portals (such as IPCHEM) and inventories performed in HBM4EU or PARC due to their scopes and methods of data collection, validation and harmonisation,
- Related lack of interoperability of resulting information,
- Non-trivial links between the monitoring programmes and databases (some programmes do not have official data portals, some report to databases gathering data from multiple programmes),
- Related problems with the data ownership and responsible contact points,
- Potential duplicities in data reported to multiple databases,
- Excessive burden for the data managers when reporting to multiple project databases,
- Findability of national monitoring programmes and databases,
- Availability of information on short-term monitoring projects and environmental monitoring and biomonitoring elements in population studies,
- Extending inventories to the programmes outside Europe,
- Long-term sustainability of selected solutions (technical solutions, hosting) and procedures (interlinks with existing data portals and infrastructures).

Steps to be taken in Y2:

- to organize a joint workshop to strengthen a collaboration between PARC WP 4 (T4.1 and T4.2), WP 7, and WP 9,
- to design/test/approve the architecture of the pilot PARC Data Hub, specifically the element for inventories of monitoring resources,
- to refine the scope of the WP 9.1 and 9.2 activities, expected outcomes and the interactions with IPCHEM and other existing inventories described in previous sections,
- to revise/harmonise a structure of metadata to be gathered from environmental and HBM studies,
- to refine a strategy for the gathering metadata from environmental monitoring and HBM studies,
- to discuss the technical aspects facilitating the exchange of information between the PARC Data Hub and other sources including IPCHEM to avoid that duplicate information is collected from data owners,

- to define common strategies to validate data collected from different sources,
- to agree on joint criteria for the inclusion of the studies into the future database/inventory
- to re-assess studies collected so far according to the defined criteria, add missing information, and develop the initial inventory.